

Winfried Sebald's *Austerlitz* (2001) and His Reflections on Theresienstadt in Light of Resi Weglein's Eyewitness Account and *Memoirs* (1945)

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Abstract

The highly reputed novel or literary documentary *Austerlitz* (2001) by Winfried. G. Sebald has attracted much critical respect and high praise. Sebald worked intensively with various sources reflecting on the Holocaust, and one of those, H. G. Adler's *Theresienstadt 1941–1945* (first published in 1955), formed the backbone of *Austerlitz*. One of the surviving prisoners in Theresienstadt, Resi Weglein, who had been a nurse from Ulm, managed to return home after the war in 1945 together with her husband, Siego Weglein, and she sat down soon after to compose her memoirs. Those were finally published in 1988, accompanied by a detailed historical analysis of the history of antisemitism in Ulm and the environs since the early nineteenth century by the local historians Silvester Lechner and Alfred Moos. Those two scholars relied, in turn, heavily on Adler's detailed study, but Sebald scholars have not yet known of these intriguing connections. Since these memoirs are soon going to be published for the first time in an English translation, it seems to be most pertinent to bring both texts into conversation with each other and thus to add further to our understanding of this famous novel in light of Resi's writing.

Keywords: *W. G. Sebald, Resi Weglein, Concentration Camp Theresienstadt, Holocaust, memory studies, memoirs.*

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Introduction

The protagonist of Sebald's famous novel, *Austerlitz* (2001), Jacques Austerlitz, had survived the Holocaust because his Czech parents had sent him, then still an infant, on one of the last *Kindertransporte* (children's transports) from Prague to London. The novel sets in with him traveling as a middle-aged man back to the Continent and exploring architectural history – his professional interest – and then also his personal background. The memory of his past seems to have been wiped out once he had been adopted by an elderly Welsh Nonconformist preacher and his sickly and then moribund wife and spent his childhood near Bala, Gwynedd (northwestern Wales) (Hein 2014, 490–518). Like Austerlitz, Sebald spent his formative (adult) years in England, earning his doctorate there and embarking on his academic career. The novel, however, traces the protagonist's journey back into his past via constant examinations of historical monuments, such as train stations and then, ultimately, Theresienstadt.

Once confronted with the local conditions in Prague, however and meeting the elderly lady Vera, a friend of his mother, Agàta, and also his own caretaker then, he slowly but surely rediscovers his childhood history, and he can even retrieve some of his original Czech language. His mother, an actress and opera singer, had been deported to the Theresienstadt concentration camp and was then sent to Auschwitz into her death. After Austerlitz's return to London, he manages to secure a copy of the Nazi propaganda film *Theresienstadt: Ein Dokumentarfilm aus dem jüdischen Siedlungsgebiet* (1944). Although he believes to have

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identified his mother in one of the screens, Vera later dismisses that and demonstrates this with the help of a photo showing his mother as an actress.

Sebald and Theresienstadt

Sebald had learned about the historical aspects of these *Kindertransporte* through a BBC production, *Susi's Story*, which in turn had been based on the memoirs by Rosa Bechhöfer, *Whatever Happened to Susi?* (edited by Jeremy Josephs), released on January 3, 1991, and used it as a major source for his novel, *Austerlitz*, if we can really call it a 'novel.' The documentary told the story of the 3-year-old twins Lotte and Susi Bechhöfer who had arrived in London in 1939. All these children on the *Kindertransporte* were sent away by their Jewish parents from Germany, Austria, or the Czech Republic in the hope that they could thus survive the Holocaust, whereas they themselves faced certain death (Curio 2006; Hofreiter 2010; Dunkel 2022; for a most detailed discussion of the background, organization, and results, see <https://encyclopedia.ushmm.org/content/en/article/kindertransport-1938-40>; last accessed on 14 Oct. 2024).

The city of Hamburg has dedicated a moving memorial to these *Kindertransporte* outside of the Dammtor train station (South exit), created by Frank Meisler and Arie Ovadia in 2015. Resi and Siego Weglein followed the example of many Jewish families and had their two sons, Walter and Heinz, shipped to the Netherlands. Most of these kids died, even if they found some hiding places. Walter, one of the few survivors, later moved to New York, gained a Ph.D. in Chemistry, and late in his life created, together with his famous wife Michi, a Weglyn Endowed Chair for Multicultural Studies at Cal Poly Pomona, California (see also below; for background see <https://www.cpp.edu/class/weglyn/index.shtml>) – he had adapted his name to an easier English spelling. In 2022, the then holder of that Chair, Dr. Mary Kunmi Yu Danico, commissioned me to do a translation of these memoirs and the accompanying historical analysis, which are now soon to appear in print with Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

We have long recognized the great literary brilliance of Sebald's novel, as scholarship has richly confirmed. Being partly a sort of autobiography, partly a historical quest back into the protagonist's past, and being partly also a major literary enterprise to probe one's collapsing and deconstructed identity in the post-war world (Bauer 2006), *Austerlitz* has struck most critics as deeply meaningful in the effort to come to terms with the trauma the Holocaust survivors continue to go through. The fact that Austerlitz is a researcher of architectural history lends particular weight to his search for his past home, identity, and culture, a faint construction that had been created by his parents and community in Prague during his early childhood and then was destroyed by the Nazis in the Holocaust (Angier 2021; Kaufmann 2023; Schütte, ed., 2023).

Theresienstadt plays a central role in Austerlitz's quest for his parents because it had been the location where a vast number of Jewish people from all over Europe had been forcefully deported irrespective of their age and health, readying them to send them off to their death in other camps. Nevertheless, the Nazis had created a movie about this concentration camp to pretend to the world that it and countless other camps were 'housing units' that provided the elderly with some kind of retreat from their ordinary life and good care in their old age. The ideological propaganda was nothing but a bitter mockery by the Nazi killing machine, for which the transitory camp in Theresienstadt was a critical launching pad (<https://perspectives.ushmm.org/item/theresienstadt-a-documentary-film-1944>).

Some of the survivors, including those who had been sent away by their parents to rescue them from the Nazis, published their memories, and Sebald utilized some of those (Josephs with Bechhöfer 1999), especially when they dealt with the *Kindertransporte*. The captives in the concentration camp had to struggle hard to survive, and a large majority of them simply passed away under the harsh, brutal, if not murderous conditions. Some, however, turned to the creative arts, such as Gisela Rottonara, who published her illustrated diary in 2024. Gerty Spies spent her time in the camp composing poetry about her experiences in that horrible location which appeared in print in 1947. Recently, Berthie Philipp came out with a novel focused on this concentration camp (2023). The life of Doctor Hans Wienskowitz who died there was

documented by Christine Lipp-Peetz (2021/23). Mary Steinhauser published a necrolog of the dead in Theresienstadt (1987), and Wolfgang Benz wrote a history of the concentration camp.

To all these valuable studies and personal documents, we can now add the memoirs of Resi Weglein, who had composed those shortly after her return to Ulm in 1945 (Weglein 1988/1990). These memoirs are most valuable for the history of Theresienstadt because of the author's sober, though not unempathetic discussion and descriptions of what she and her husband had to go through, along with countless other prisoners. They also had sent their two sons away to Holland in one of those *Kindertransporte*, which now brings us back to Sebald's famous novel. To remind ourselves, his protagonist had been one of those children, but growing up in Wales, he lost all memories of his origin, language, family, and history, and only the long and painful research on Theresienstadt makes it possible for him to find himself once again. Traumas like this one require intensive labor and is associated with much pain, but it seems that despite Austerlitz's best efforts to cope with his own trauma and perhaps to overcome it, the confrontation with the remnants of the concentration camp, a site of horrible human tragedy defeats all that (Schwamborn 2017, pp. 200–35, 239–61).

We should not read Sebald's *Austerlitz* without being somewhat familiar with contemporary sources on this concentration camp (cf. also Schwertfeger 1989; Schiff with McLaughlin, 2017; Darling 2023). While Adler offered a meticulous overview of the history of the concentration camp of Theresienstadt, which he himself had survived, as well as a short stint in Auschwitz (Filkins 2013), Weglein's memoirs can serve us exceedingly well as a historical-literary source offering deep insights into the actual conditions the miserable and completely innocent prisoners suffered from. Of course, Resi was not the only one who tried her best to come to terms with the traumatic experience, if we think, for instance, of her colleague, the fellow nurse Ruth Rieser (1987). In fact, Theresienstadt was almost like a 'nursing home' for the elderly, except for the absolutely miserable living conditions disregarding any respect for human life (Brush 2004; Shlain 2020), and the term 'nursing' would be an utter cynicism. As much as the Gestapo later tried to project the camp as a pleasant resort for the elderly Jews, the essential purpose was the extermination of all Jewish people. Theresienstadt was, to repeat myself, not a decimation camp, but a transitory station toward death for most of its inmates. There are thousands of memorial stones in German sidewalks, the so-called "Stolpersteine". One example that I recently found in downtown Göttingen (Weendter Landstraße) in June of 2024 was dedicated to an Anneliese Gräfenberg; she was born in 1903, fled from Göttingen to the Czech Republic in 1937, but then was taken prisoner by the Gestapo in 1942 and shipped to Theresienstadt, and the next year she was sent to Auschwitz to her death. One of countless other very similar destinies and tragic cases.

Resi Weglein's Memoirs

Once the English translation of Resi Weglein's memoirs will be available in English translation, we will have direct access to one of the most detailed reports about the concentration camp in Theresienstadt. That one, in turn, will enable us to study much more meticulously what Austerlitz in Sebald's novel is going through really, and what he knows or learns in time about what his mother had to suffer. Of course, the modern spectator can only read about those horrible events from a historical perspective, but the combination of Resi's memoirs and Sebald's famous novel facilitates a much more insightful examination of the literary text, adding, above all, a direct line of communication to the historical events. Her text is a direct eyewitness account; whereas the novel builds on various correlated texts, all focusing on the unhuman conditions in Theresienstadt where the goal really consisted of making the inmates suffer so badly that they would die on their own.

In Sebald's novel, for the protagonist, educated as an architectural historian, the concentration camp is just that, at first sight, a constructed prison camp, but the spaces that open up before his own eyes soon fill with his personal history, that is, the memories of his mother. In fact, Resi's memoirs easily prove to be eerie confirmation for all the details mentioned in *Austerlitz*, but they go much more into detail and describe the actual living (or dying) conditions there. Sebald has obviously done good research, drawing

from the best source available, Adler's study (see above). Now, we will soon have Resi's memories copied down in 1945 also available in an English translation. There we learn about the daily grind, the famine, the sicknesses spreading quickly, the lack of water, the waiting at long lines, the constant experience of death, the meetings of Jews from other parts of Europe, the pretenses by the Nazis when they allowed representatives of the Swiss Red Cross to visit the camp, which by then had been temporarily 'beautified' so as to make it look like a spa for retirees.

Resi Weglein composed an impressive narrative that at times almost might sound like Dante's *Inferno* (ca. 1320) where the protagonist, guided by the Roman poet Virgil, travels through the underworld and witnesses all the horrible punishments meted out to sinners. Here just a few examples from my current English translation:

Now you are certainly in the Inferno. There was endless humming and grumbling, crying and shrieking, there was an odd semi-dark because only a few light bulbs were hanging from the ceiling. On the floor, there were very strong beams you had to step over. If your steps were not high enough and you did not pay attention, you fell down and hurt yourself badly. It was very common that the old people broke their upper thigh bones. Of course, there were no beds; you had to sit down on the naked raw rocks covered with the dirt of many years (Weglein, unnumbered so far).

Or:

Several people who had committed suicide because their nerves could no longer sustain the conditions we no longer tried to bring back to life. The first to die were Mr. Landgerichtsdirektor [County Court Director] Hermann Wolf from Karlsruhe, Mr. Dr. Josef Reis from Heidelberg, Mr. Frischmann from Vienna, Mr. Landau from Vienna, Mr. Dr. Hermann Netter from Mannheim. The beds could not be cleaned after they had died because the carriers of the sick immediately brought new sick people in after they had fetched the corpses down from the attic. Up there they did not yet have beds, and the nurses could not cope with all the work. In that attic, many, many people died every day. Many voluntarily put an end to their lives by throwing themselves off the balcony and the windows in the attic. Those who had fallen down looked grisly, with all their bones broken. We had become so hardened already then that we admired without regret, yes, almost with envy, their courage with which they had resolved to commit suicide (Weglein, unnumbered so far).

However, Resi was carried by a strong faith in God, and by her resolve to do everything in her power to help other people in the camp:

During those days I doubted divine justice and was literally despondent. I have to write this down because I am ashamed of my small mind still today. The work with the sick people helped me to find my way back. I quickly realized that I had to go through all those tests in order to gain my inner freedom. Every suffering, all misery, including sickness, I had to suffer through in my own body so that I could be for others what I conceived of as being a [true] "nurse." More about that only at the end of my memories! (Weglein)

Austerlitz in Sebald's novel, by contrast, observes the architectural remnants of the concentration camp, critically surveys the sources about that horrible Nazi site, but it remains impossible for him, or for Sebald as the author, truly to represent the horrible situation the vast number of innocent victims had to suffer from in Theresienstadt. Of course, Austerlitz has to cope with his own trauma, having been sent away by his own parents to save him from their destiny, so his perspective is, naturally, the one of an exile who could survive growing up in England during that time. Resi, however, focuses in her memoirs primarily on her own experiences in the camp; she never talks about her sons who had escaped in 1939; she even hardly mentions her husband, Siego, who was also sent to Theresienstadt and luckily later returned home to Ulm with her.

So, the comparison leaves us with the curious but deeply intriguing situation that Sebald as the novelist basically picks up where Resi Weglein had left off. The two historians, Silvester Lechner und Alfred Moos, however, provided the historical background in rough sketches the history of the Weglein family, whereas Sebald retells the psychological drama of the surviving child trying to retrace his history and that of his mother in Theresienstadt and his father somewhere else. In many different ways, we recognize here an amazing narrative correlation that will greatly strengthen our understanding of Sebald's novel and

increase our appreciation of his biographical and psychologizing efforts. Of course, the differences in genres are obvious, and since there is no firm evidence that Sebald might have been familiar with Resi's text – he primarily relied on Adler's historical study – the purpose here was not to move the memoirs into the range of the possible sources for the novel. Instead, we can recognize Resi's memoirs as powerful narrative reflections on her own suffering and that of hundreds of thousands of other Jews in that concentration camp that certainly underlay the experiences by the fictional character Austerlitz. The literary and historical concatenations of both works are rather significant and, once fully realized, will promise to open a new chapter in Sebald research.

The Afterlife

The final irony of history in this regard proves to be the fact that Walter Weglein/Weglyn then married Michi Nishiura in 1950 who had been imprisoned in one of the infamous Japanese American internment camps during the Second World War (Gila River, Arizona) and later wrote the famous and greatly influential study about her ghastly experiences, *Years of Infamy* (Michi Weglyn 1976), appropriately called, because of its huge impact on American politics, the "Bible of the Redress Movement" (https://encyclopedia.densho.org/Michi_Nishiura_Weglyn/). Late in life, the couple made a major donation to Cal Poly at Pomona to establish an Endowed Chair of Multicultural Studies in 1999, and this in turn ultimately made possible the translation of Resi Weglein's memoirs into English.

Sebald himself had explained the purpose of literature in a speech opening the Stuttgart Literaturhaus on Nov. 17, 2001 stating, "Einzig vielleicht dazu, daß wir uns erinnern und daß wir begreifen lernen, daß es sonderbare, von keiner Kausallogik zu ergründende Zusammenhänge gibt" (quoted from Filkins, 2013, 161; in his translation: "Perhaps only to remember, and teach us to understand that some strange connections cannot be explained by causal logic"; see also <https://sebald.wordpress.com/2014/05/03/literaturhaus-stuttgart/>). If we could accept that approach, only minus the exclusionary claim, then Resi Weglein's memoirs deserve to stand right next to the historical account by H. G. Adler and then also ought to be acknowledged as a major narrative memory right next to Sebald's famous *Austerlitz*.

Undoubtedly, as scholars have emphasized numerous times, this novel belongs centrally to the literary movement or effort to come to terms with the Holocaust today, an impossibility by itself and yet fundamentally important for the present generation (see, e.g., Gray 2017, 258–72). The publication of the English translation of Resi's memoirs, however, will assist us critically in that regard and broaden the basis for a deeper understanding of the constant struggles by Austerlitz as outlined by Sebald. The conversation between both works underscores once again, as Edit Kovács has recently pointed out, citing Sebald himself, that literature itself ought to be understood as a narrative platform to explore human ethics and morality, hence our identity, culture, and history. Any other approach transforms a fictional text into a form of entertainment work (Kovács 2021, 7). Whereas Austerlitz approaches Theresienstadt as a visitor, as a spectator of the horrendous suffering in that concentration camp, not really able to fathom what had happened there in terms of human suffering, Resi's personal reflections flesh it all out most painfully and directly.

Conclusion

We can now gain deeper insights into the sources that formed the basis of W. G. Sebald's novel through Resi Weglein's memoirs. Whereas Sebald developed a fictionalizing account involving Theresienstadt, Resi Weglein provided a highly moving and yet also sober account of what had happened in the concentration camp of Theresienstadt. Her work and the critical analysis by the two historians need to be read next to Sebald's text, which had sensitized us already to the horror of the Holocaust. Sebald was apparently not familiar with these memoirs, but those had certainly influenced the report by Adler. Having the English translation available, will add significantly to the understanding of Sebald's message.

The combination of both works allows for a remarkable intertextual approach to Holocaust Studies from a German literary and historical perspective.

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